

A New Self-Tuning Fuzzy PD Controller of a BDFIG for Wind Energy Conversion

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Abstract : In this paper presents a new control scheme to control a brushless doubly fed induction generator (BDFIG) using back-to-back PWM converters for wind power generation. The proposed control scheme is a New Self-Tuning Fuzzy Proportional-Derivative Controller (NSTFPDC). The goal of BDFIG control is to achieve a similar dynamic performance to the doubly fed induction generator (DFIG), exploiting the well-known induction machine vector control philosophy. The performance of NSTFPDC controller has been investigated and compared with the two controllers, called Proportional-Integral (PI) and PD-like Fuzzy Logic controller (PD-like FLC) based BDFIG. The simulation results demonstrate the effectiveness and the robustness of the NSTFPDC controller.

Keywords : brushless doubly fed induction generator (BDFIG), PI controller, PD-like fuzzy logic controller, new self-tuning fuzzy proportional-derivative controller (NSTFPDC), scaling factor, back-to-back PWM converters, wind energy system

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014